

Project number: 730879

Project acronym: INFRAFRONTIER2020

D4.4 Display of validated mouse models of human diseases on the INFRAFRONTIER portal (Month 48) (CNR)

URL of the deliverable:

https://www.infrafrontier.eu/search?keyword=browse_human_diseases

Brief Description for the deliverable:

This deliverable addresses 'WP4 Task 2 Data annotation and validating mouse models of human disease'. Curators have set up and applied specific curatorial procedures and carried out the accurate annotation and validation of INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA mutant strain resources with representation of modelled human diseases. The process has involved the systematic analysis and classification of published mutant strain's genotypic and phenotypic data and related model descriptions, also taking advantage of effective feedback and support by the original strain producers. The curators have thus implemented the assignment, validation, listing and updating of specific EMMA model annotations, with association to relevant records in international human diseases and phenotype model resources (MGI, Disease Ontology, OMIM, ORPHANET, Human Phenotype Ontology, Mammalian Phenotype Ontology, IMPC). The model datasets are being constantly reviewed and updated, taking in consideration new published data, novel personal information from the strain producers, etc.

The curated EMMA resources currently include over 480 distinct models of human diseases, with mutant allele and/or transgene composition matching the relevant MGI records. The curated EMMA resources also allow integrated user's access to relevant MGI gene data, DO, OMIM, ORPHANET and PubMed records and include appropriate references to model's background/zygosity variations that may modulate phenotypic/pathological traits. The curated EMMA records currently identify other 400+ strains with matching mutant genes and related allelic composition (e.g. targeted conditional alleles vs. constitutive knock-out alleles), which is instrumental for the production of novel, refined disease models.

The annotation and validation of EMMA disease models requires the accurate assignment and classification of relevant Mammalian Phenotype (MP) Ontology , terms. The INFRAFRONTIER IT group has thus implemented the programmatic acquisition, updating and public presentation of current gene- and allele/transgene-specific MP annotations pertinent to the EMMA strains, from both MGI's and IMPC's phenotypic data resources. These include >33000 MGI-assigned and >8700 IMPC-assigned, allele-specific annotations, which are associated to >5500 EMMA strains.

The manual annotation and validation of INFRAFRONTIER-EMMA disease model resources strongly promotes and expands their global dissemination and use, thus effectively contributing to the sustainability of INFRAFRONTIER.

Screenshots of the deliverable

EMMA strain's disease model and MP annotations from MGI and IMPC resources

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